

Occlusal Veneers: A Minimally Invasive Restorative Option for Posterior Tooth Rehabilitation – A Narrative Review

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Abstract

Occlusal veneers are gaining widespread recognition as a conservative and biomimetic treatment modality for restoring posterior teeth affected by wear, erosion, or structural compromise. Unlike traditional full coverage crowns, occlusal veneers require minimal tooth reduction and allow preservation of enamel and dentin, thereby enhancing the longevity and biomechanical performance of restorations. This narrative review presents a comprehensive examination of occlusal veneers, discussing their classification, indications, preparation techniques, material options, biomechanical behavior, clinical limitations, and future prospects based on the current literature.

Introduction

Preserving tooth structure is critical for the longevity of teeth and restorations. It is advantageous to preserve pulp vitality and delay the need for invasive interventions such as endodontic therapy, posts, and cores, which negatively affect the long-term success of restored teeth. With advancements in optical and mechanical properties of ceramics, CAD/CAM techniques, and adhesive systems, the philosophy of restoration has shifted from aggressive reduction to a more conservative, pathology driven approach.¹

The minimally invasive dentistry (MID) approach is pivotal in modern prosthodontics, especially for posterior teeth susceptible to attrition, erosion, and parafunctional habits. Full coverage crowns, while once the gold standard, necessitate excessive removal of tooth structure. In contrast, occlusal veneers are extra-coronal restorations with minimal preparation requirements and provide superior biological, mechanical, and esthetic benefits.²

Background

Occlusal veneers, also termed veneerlays or vonlays, are fabricated from ceramic, hybrid, or composite materials and restore occlusal morphology without encroaching excessively on axial tooth surfaces.³ Studies have demonstrated that occlusal veneers preserve more dentin and enamel than crowns, with as little as 1 mm of reduction necessary for success (Edelhoff & Sorensen, 2002). Their long-term survival has been reported as 88.7% over 17 years and 84% over 12 years⁵, supporting their durability. They are particularly advantageous for young patients, esthetically demanding cases, and post endodontic restorations.⁶

Occlusal Veneers

These are extra coronal restorations demanding an easy preparation determined by occlusal anatomy and provision of adequate interocclusal clearance, they were first described by Pascal Magne.¹ They may be also called tabletop restorations. Ultrathin CAD-CAM occlusal veneers which are about 1 - 1.3 mm at the cusp tip and 0.4 - 0.6 mm thick at the central grooves; had been recognized as a better substitute to full crowns. One study used occlusal veneers as re enameling process for replacement of missed enamel in cases with sever erosion.⁷

Three preparation designs of occlusal veneers have been described by Samaa Kotb et al 2019⁸.

In the conventional planar occlusal veneer preparation, the occlusal surface is reduced by 1.5 mm at the cusp tips and 1 mm at the central fossae, without any intra-coronal cavity, axial wall preparation, margin preparation, or defined taper.(Figure 1 a 2a)

In the modified occlusal veneer preparation with a circumferential finish line the occlusal reduction remains the same (1.5 mm at cusp tips and 1 mm at central fossae), but in addition, 1 mm axial walls are prepared with

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a 1 mm deep chamfer margin, and the axial walls are given an 8° taper.(figure 1b, 2b)

In the modified occlusal veneer preparation with an intra-coronal cavity, the occlusal reduction is again 1.5 mm at cusp tips and 1 mm at fossae, but here a 2 mm intra-coronal cavity is prepared with 8° occlusal divergence, without axial wall or margin preparation.(Figure 1c, 2c)

Figure 1: Preparation Design for Occlusal Veneer

Figure 2: Cemented Occlusal Veneer

Clinical Indications

- To manage progressive enamel loss due to physiological aging or accelerated by pathological conditions like bio-corrosion, erosion, and bruxism.
- When there is significant tooth structure loss that may or may not be associated with a reduction in vertical occlusal dimension.
- To preserve remaining tooth structure, as invasive treatments may disrupt the biological and biomechanical balance, risking long-term failure.

In cases of severe tooth wear, where there is compromise in:

- Masticatory function
- Esthetics
- Occlusal vertical dimension
- Facial profile
- When conservative, additive adhesive techniques are preferred, offering minimally invasive alternatives.
- For partial or total cusp coverage depending on the degree of tooth destruction, especially in scenarios where pulp health and occlusal stability are at risk.

Contraindications

- 1. Insufficient Enamel for Bonding:** Occlusal veneers rely on adhesive bonding, which requires an adequate enamel substrate for long-term success. In cases with severe enamel loss or exposed dentin, bonding strength may be compromised.
- 2. Uncontrolled Parafunctional Habits (e.g., Severe Bruxism):** Patients with untreated or severe bruxism are at higher risk of restoration fracture or debonding, especially with glass-ceramics. While some materials like zirconia are more resistant, occlusal veneers may still not be the best option without a protective protocol (e.g., night guards).
- 3. Poor Oral Hygiene and High Caries Risk:** Patients with poor plaque control or a history of recurrent caries may experience marginal leakage, secondary decay, and restoration failure

4. Severe Tooth Malposition or Inadequate Occlusal Clearance: In cases where teeth are malaligned or occlusal space is limited, proper veneer placement and function may not be achievable without prior orthodontic or occlusal adjustment.

5. Extensive Tooth Destruction: When the remaining tooth structure is severely compromised, a full-coverage crown or other restorative option may offer better protection and function than a partial occlusal veneer.

6. Incompatible Occlusal Schemes (e.g., unstable posterior support): Occlusal veneers may fail in patients with unbalanced or unstable occlusions, particularly if posterior support is lacking.

Materials Used for Occlusal Veneers

The selection of restorative material is a critical factor in determining the success, durability, and esthetic outcome of occlusal veneers. Several material options are available, each with unique mechanical and clinical properties suited for different clinical scenarios.

Lithium disilicate, commercially known as IPS e.max, is widely used due to its excellent esthetics, translucency, and high flexural strength of approximately 470 MPa.⁹ Its optical properties closely mimic natural enamel, making it ideal for restorations in esthetically demanding regions. Lithium disilicate also allows for thin restorations (as low as 1.0 mm) while maintaining sufficient mechanical integrity, making it a popular choice for both posterior and anterior occlusal veneers.

Zirconia, particularly in its monolithic form, is another highly favored material for occlusal veneers due to its exceptional strength and resistance to fracture. It exhibits a flexural strength of around 800 MPa, which makes it suitable for high load posterior areas where masticatory forces are significant.¹⁰ Although slightly less translucent than lithium disilicate, newer generations of translucent zirconia have improved in esthetic performance, expanding their indications.

The principal limitation of zirconia with respect to adhesive bonding lies in its polycrystalline, silica-free structure, which lacks a glassy phase. As a result, zirconia does not respond to conventional acid etching or silane coupling agents, rendering traditional bonding strategies ineffective and necessitating alternative surface treatments and adhesive systems for durable adhesion.^{11,12}

Composite resins are also utilized, particularly for their favorable elastic modulus, which closely approximates that of natural dentin (around 16–20 GPa vs. dentin's 17.7–29.8 GPa). This biomechanical compatibility contributes to better stress distribution and fatigue resistance under occlusal load.³ In addition, composite veneers offer advantages such as ease of intraoral repair, reduced cost, and chairside adaptability, making them a practical option in many clinical settings.

A key limitation of composite resin in bonded restorations is its comparatively low wear resistance, with annual volumetric wear rates reported in the range of 20–50 μm , which is significantly higher than ceramics (<10 $\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$) and natural enamel (~10–20 $\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$). This susceptibility to wear can adversely affect occlusal stability, surface morphology, and the long-term clinical performance of restorations.¹³⁻¹⁵

Advancements in CAD/CAM technology and hybrid materials have further broadened the scope for occlusal veneers, offering enhanced accuracy, strength, and conservative preparation protocols. The selection among these materials should be guided

by the clinical situation, esthetic requirements, functional demands, and the patient's parafunctional habits.

Sherif Sultan et al. (JIDMR)¹⁶ proposed a classification based on restoration extent:

- Porcelain laminate veneer: a thin, bonded ceramic restoration that restores the facial, incisal, and part of the proximal surfaces of teeth requiring esthetic restoration;
- Inlay: a fixed intracoronal restoration; a dental restoration made outside of a tooth to correspond to the form of the prepared cavity, which is then luted into the tooth
- Table top: covers only the occlusal surface
- Vonlay/Veneerlay: First described by Edward McLaren et al, vonlays are hybrid restorations made of monolithic lithium disilicate combining features of an onlay and a buccal veneer, typically used in posterior teeth with occlusal and buccal surface damage or wear. Their key advantages include reduced technique sensitivity, minimal invasiveness, and improved reparability compared to full-coverage crowns.¹⁷
- Onlay: - a partial-coverage restoration that restores one or more cusps and adjoining occlusal surfaces or the entire occlusal surface and is retained by mechanical or adhesive means
- Overlay: overlay is prosthesis that tends to restore the occlusal cusp integrity of a tooth. It crosses beyond the occlusal table in cervical direction.
- Minimally invasive posterior indirect restoration (MIPIR): this is a restoration that does not have a specific shape or preparation and it is not an onlay, partial coverage crown or endocrown.

Bonded onlays and vonlays are indicated in extensive occlusal wear, cracked tooth syndrome, or large restorations. Unlike conventional MOD onlays, these follow defect specific, non-retentive designs with rounded internal forms. Specific kits such as Komet's 4665 facilitate precise reduction. Vonlays offer functional and esthetic benefits, particularly in posterior wear.

Endocrowns: introduced by Bindl and Mormann (1999)¹⁸, are monolithic, pulp-chamber retained restorations ideal for post-endodontic molars with inadequate ferrule. They provide better stress distribution and require less time and cost.¹⁹ Resin ceramics and lithium disilicate are preferred materials.²⁰

Figure 3: Different types for minimally invasive restorations

Marginal Adaptation and Adhesion

The success and longevity of occlusal veneers are heavily dependent on the precision of marginal adaptation and the effectiveness of the adhesive protocol. With the advent of advanced CAD/CAM technologies, it is now possible to achieve highly accurate restorations with marginal gaps measuring less than 120 μm , which are well within clinically acceptable limits.²¹ Such precision minimizes the risk of microleakage, secondary caries, and marginal discoloration.

Among various preparation designs, rounded shoulder margins have demonstrated superior marginal integrity compared to chamfer or feather edge margins. This design supports the ceramic material evenly and enhances the fit of the restoration at the tooth restoration interface.

Adhesion plays an equally critical role in the success of occlusal veneers. The use of total etch or self-etch adhesive protocols, combined with high quality resin cements, ensures strong and durable bonding. However, achieving a predictable bond depends heavily on proper moisture control during the bonding procedure. Studies have shown that both over dried and excessively wet dentin surfaces can compromise bond strength, leading to increased risk of adhesive failure.²² Thus, optimal surface conditioning and controlled isolation are imperative during the adhesive cementation of occlusal veneers.

Biomechanical Guidelines for Preparation of Bonded all Ceramic Restoration^{23,24}

- 1. Simplicity of Preparation Geometry:** The cavity or preparation design should remain as simple and conservative as possible, avoiding unnecessary retentive features or complex internal geometry
- 2. Adequate and Uniform Material Thickness:** The restorative material must be provided with sufficient and uniform thickness in all areas, particularly in the occlusal and axial regions, to ensure structural durability and resistance to fracture.
- 3. Smooth Internal Line Angles and Transitions:** All internal line angles should be rounded and transitions between surfaces should be gradual, thereby minimizing stress concentration within the restoration.
- 4. Optimization of Stress Distribution:** The preparation should be designed to reduce tensile stresses and, where feasible, to redirect occlusal forces into more favorable compressive stresses.
- 5. Avoidance of Stress Concentration Zones:** Sudden changes in wall inclination, thickness reduction, or sharp edges should be avoided, as these create localized stress peaks detrimental to the longevity of the restoration.
- 6. Elimination of Notch Effects:** Any notches, sharp indentations, or irregularities that could act as crack initiation sites must be eliminated from the preparation design.
- 7. Maximization of Adhesive Bonding Surface:** A broad and continuous bonding interface between the restoration and the tooth structure should be ensured in order to enhance adhesion and improve biomechanical stability.
- 8. Placement of Margins in Enamel Whenever Possible:** Preparation margins should be located within enamel, wherever clinically feasible, to maximize adhesive effectiveness and ensure long-term marginal integrity.

Discussion

In restorative dentistry, two principal paradigms guide clinical decision making: the conventional approach, which relies on mechanical or frictional retention, and the minimally invasive (MI) or adhesive approach, which emphasizes tooth preservation and relies on adhesive bonding. While conventional restorations, such as full crowns, have long-standing clinical success, they often necessitate extensive tooth reduction and are typically fabricated from both esthetic and non-esthetic materials. In contrast, minimally invasive restorations are almost exclusively fabricated from esthetic materials like ceramics or composites and aim to preserve as much natural tooth structure as possible.³

A significant challenge in minimally invasive dentistry lies in

nomenclature and classification, which often causes confusion among clinicians and dental technicians. Terms such as overlay, tabletop, ceramic onlay, bonded onlay, occlusal veneer, and ultrathin veneer are frequently used interchangeably, despite variations in preparation design, extent of coverage, and restorative intent. For example, vonlays a hybrid of veneer and onlay are used to restore occluso-buccal surfaces in posterior teeth and are particularly suitable for esthetic and functional rehabilitation with minimal invasiveness (McLaren et al., 2015). Other evolving terms like endocrowns, crownlays, and sharonlays have emerged to describe specific combinations of coverage types, highlighting the dynamic evolution of minimally invasive prosthodontics.¹⁸

While these terminological distinctions may appear academic, they have practical implications for treatment planning, communication, and education. An agreed upon classification would streamline case selection, preparation design, and material choice. Until then, clinicians must rely on a thorough assessment of the individual clinical situation to select the appropriate minimally invasive restoration.

Key factors to evaluate during planning include:

- Adhesive potential: The quality and quantity of remaining enamel are crucial for successful bonding.
- Parafunctional habits: Bruxism or clenching can compromise the longevity of bonded restorations.
- Posterior bite force: Molars are subjected to higher masticatory loads, influencing material selection.
- Opposing dentition: The wear pattern of opposing teeth must be considered to avoid excessive wear or failure.
- Isolation feasibility: Achieving a dry, contaminant free field is essential for effective adhesive bonding.
- Bonding protocol reliability: Strict adherence to adhesive protocols ensures long-term restoration success.

In conclusion, while minimally invasive restorations present an exciting alternative to traditional crowns, their success relies on meticulous clinical judgment, case selection, and adherence to evolving material science and adhesive techniques.

Conclusion

When a posterior tooth requires cuspal coverage, full crowns should not be the default choice. PMI FDPs like onlays, vonlays and occlusal veneers offer conservative alternatives with adequate success rates. Proper planning, material selection, and adhesive techniques are critical. Full crowns should be limited to crown replacement, implants, or post-core scenarios.

Limitations and Future Research

Despite in vitro support, occlusal veneers lack long-term clinical validation:

- Few RCTs or prospective clinical trials
- Limited data on failure modes
- Need for periodontal and biofilm studies
- Standardized digital protocols yet to be defined

Future research should focus on long-term follow-up, digital workflows, and bioactive materials to further validate occlusal veneer therapies.

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